

Gary Snyder's "Real Work": Educational Implications

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As a seminal figure in the movement toward Buddhism that "took off in the 1960s" (Seager, 1999, p. 9), Gary Snyder has offered one of the clearest expressions of Buddhist sensibility in American literature. He helped transfer Buddhist values to the West by linking Buddhism to what he calls "the most archaic values on earth" (Snyder, 1978, p. viii), which acknowledge the basis of spiritual being and political action in nature, in the pattern of deep-ecological "ethical holism" (James, 2004, p. 72-82). Snyder thus sees in Buddhism hints of ancient animistic beliefs, and explores these variations on Buddhist practice through what he calls "the real work," a system of actions and attitudes that accords with natural occurrences and their spiritual significance.¹ Here is how Snyder describes the real work: "[t]he real work is what we really do.... [I]f we can live the work we have to do, knowing that we are real, and it's real, and that the world is real, then it becomes right. And that's the *real work*: to make the world as real as it is, and to find ourselves as real as we are within it.... The real work [is also to] take the struggle on without the *least* hope of doing any good. To check the destruction of the interesting and necessary diversity of life on the planet so that the dance can go on a little better for a little longer. The other part of it is that it is always here.... The *real work* is eating each other, I suppose" (Snyder & Geneson, 1980, p. 81-82).

This description of the real work emphasizes three levels: 1) *practice*, 2) *resistance*, and 3) *resignation or acceptance*. Recalling Snyder's insistence that "work and play are one," one might argue that these three components of the real work—practice, resistance, and acceptance—illuminate a spiritual discipline that could underlie or inform a basic philosophy of education. Snyder's writing, as work, is designed to maximize awareness of nature on all planes—the mundane, the political, and the spiritual. As an ecological program, this work involves knowing cause and effect in human endeavor and understanding that human activity, or what the fourth-century B.C.E. Daoist Chuang-Tzu (2004) calls the "human," must be identical to the "work" of nature, or the "heavenly"—a distinction Chuang-Tzu makes in his work "Autumn Floods":

"What do you mean by the Heavenly and the human?"

Jo of the North Sea said, "Horses and oxen have four feet—this is what I mean by the Heavenly. Putting a halter on the horse's head, piercing the ox's nose—this is what I mean by the human."

Political, spiritual, and presumably educational work fail if they separate humanity from the natural world. Thus, Snyder's "Real Work" offers a Dharmic practice; it acknowledges the difference between the human and the heavenly and realigns the human with the heavenly, coordinating it with Buddhist practice. Importantly, as we will see, in some ways the Dharmic path reflects the basic course or experience of modern development and a modern education, and so offers both an approach to and a critical analysis of these processes. It also potentially offers philosophical perspectives that could have a significant effect on the direction of education.

Dharma and the Three Levels of “The Real Work”

The word *Dharma* means “[r]ule of duty or of social obligation (Hinduism). The truth; the saving doctrine or way (early Buddhism). Reality; essential quality; any reality (Mahayana Buddhism)” (Burt, 1955, p. 245). It derives from Sanskrit roots meaning “that which has been established in the mind” or “the object of consciousness” (Alan Hunt Badiner, qtd. in Seager, 1999, p. 211) and signifies “carrying, holding” (Fischer-Schreiber, Ehrhard & Diener, 1991, p. 54). *Dharma* in Buddhism also refers to “[t]he cosmic law, the ‘great norm’” as well as “the general state of affairs,” and “thing, phenomenon”; “[m]ental content, object of thought, idea”; and in Hinayana “the so-called factors of existence” (Fischer-Schreiber, Ehrhard & Diener, 1991, p. 54). These varied meanings suggest the ways that the concept of Dharma acknowledges Chuang-Tzu’s distinction between the human and the heavenly while it simultaneously realigns these realms.

Snyder’s “real work” corresponds with several aspects of Dharma. For instance, *practice*—including the practice of meditation—is a way to enforce resistance and to accept the “essential reality” of the heavenly, or the ongoing, undisturbed processes of nature. If we here include Zen, especially the teachings of Rinzai who saw “the roots of the concept of *dharma* in the Way of Taoism” (Molesworth, 1983, p. 79), we have a compendium of the Eastern disciplines that inform Snyder’s vision. As an expression of Dao, practice connects directly to the heavenly, since for Snyder meditation is no different from the action of animals:

At some point ... it just hit me that I really was an animal and that all of the things that we call “human” are simply part of that, including our spiritual capacities. It’s just another thing that animals can do. (Ingram, Gates, Nisker & Snyder, 1988, p. 4)

The “heavenly” connects to the Dao, and to the old precept that the scholar learns every day, while the wise man unlearns every day. “Human” experience by contrast stems from the human “distinction between the see-er and the seen” that results from nature’s “being seen as an object” (Ingram, Gates, Nisker & Snyder, 1988, p. 4). From this objectification comes power, since perceiving nature as an object leads to an attempt to control nature or even to see nature as a “social construction” (Snyder, 1999, p. 387). By reducing nature to object, science encourages the discovery of reductive and materialistic laws. Transformed into the concept of individual rights, these insights permit what Snyder calls “the mercy of the West”: social revolution.² The Westernized subject/object split rests on perceiving a difference between self and nature. If an order different from nature exists elsewhere (as in a Christian heaven), there is also an accompanying tendency to deny the self through a “willingness to accept the perceptions and decisions of others” (Snyder, 1969, p. 126)—that is, to accept authoritarianism. Authoritarianism may permit cultural or even countercultural cohesion, but at the cost of repudiating the self’s convictions and beliefs. Snyder’s resistance to “the perceptions and decisions of others” leads him in his poetry to reject an authoritative, central persona, though there is a centralized perspective.

1. Practice

Snyder stratifies his definition of “the real work” in ways that tie it to the concept of Dharma. By doing so he suggests layers of meaning to “the real work” that show the complexities of

human interactions with nature. The first concerns *practice* in the sense of a constant striving to make active connection so as to engage the world at all levels of life.³ Practice refers as much to attention to what we do in daily life as it does to any special endeavor to “connect,” the result of meditation as presented for example in Snyder’s poem “Piute Creek.” Snyder says, “The real work is what we really do ... [to] make the world as real as it is, and ... find ourselves as real as we are within it” (Snyder & Geneson, 1980, p. 81). He strives for direct involvement in nature, so that work as labor becomes another means of experiencing the earth, as does his increasing insistence on involvement with local nature, the place that one inhabits as a *grounding* counterbalance to abstract concepts, including the abstraction of “nature” itself. As a result, the realizations and levels of focus achieved in such work in many ways resemble the “practice” of sitting meditation.⁴ Acting in nature pits humanity against nature, but meditation limits “either/or” perceptions by blending mind and environment, body and breath. The result reflects the realizations, if not the erasures, reached in meditation.

For Snyder work becomes an expression of the self in nature. Work and meditation differ in that meditation allows expansion of perception while work focuses on a task, but the efficacy of each depends upon the worker or the meditator. Snyder emphasizes this devotion in his comments on the experience that led to his early poetry collection *Riprap*, in which Snyder discovered his voice as a poet. He describes how, while working in Yosemite Park, he at first tried to “exercise [his] mind” by reading Milton, then “gave up trying to carry on an intellectual interior life separate from the work.... By just working, I found myself being completely there having the whole mountain inside of me, and finally having a whole language inside of me that became one with the rocks and with the trees” (Snyder & Lampe, 1980, p. 8). “Having the whole mountain inside of me” becomes the criterion for a self in which nature and the self combine. When Snyder creates a “language ... that [is] one with the rocks and with the trees,” he assumes a fusion of humanity and nature—an identity realized in work.

Like meditation, work can hone the mind. Snyder depicts the relationship between nature and mind in his poem “No Matter, Never Mind,” in which an incestuous mix of Void, Wave, Matter and Life “Gives birth to the Mind” (Snyder, 1974, p. 11). This straightforward presentation acknowledges the Mind as a product of nature. Life recalls “The Great Mother” that Snyder later identifies as Gaia, while Matter is both brother and father to Life, its co-creator and constant companion, perhaps even a rival. As the title suggests, Mind cannot exist without Matter. The interconnection of mind and matter relieves the reader’s concerns about the origin of mind.

2. *Resistance*

This distancing from concerns about mind’s origin presents itself as a form of *resistance*, in that, if directed correctly, *resistance* itself becomes a type of *practice*. In considering mind, for instance, the *practice* of *resistance* to speculation serves as a function of Dharmic “real work” as regards that which involves the mind. Since mind develops from the material world rather than through ideas, speculation as to its origin seems fruitless. But people always immerse themselves in the abstractions that Snyder’s poetry usually counters. Humans are the creators of such abstractions as the ones in “No Matter, Never Mind,” which is why Snyder downplays the relevance of his “genealogy” even as he presents it.

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Snyder's reaction against abstractions thus implies the second level of meaning in "the real work"—*resistance*. The human tendency to abstract experience is the basis of the "human predicament" or the "problem of nature," i.e., nature as a "social construction" (Snyder, 1999, p. 387) that is configured solely as use value rather than as that self-sustaining "wildness" that Snyder at one point refers to as "self-thus" ("The Etiquette of Freedom," Snyder, 1990, p. 5), giving a literal translation of *zi-ran*, the Chinese word for nature. Snyder suggests that when humans wrongly experience nature as an abstraction, nature is abstracted from itself and becomes a creation of the human mind—a product of the human rather than of the heavenly.⁵ Yet this tendency to abstraction is the "distinction" of humanity. Such perceptions, since they represent a point of intersection in Indra's Net, retain a degree of truth. Nevertheless, any such generalization substitutes an imagined nature for phenomenal nature.

One result is expressed in Snyder's poem "Milton by Firelight." This poem from *Riprap* describes Snyder reading Milton's *Paradise Lost* at a campfire in the Sierra Nevada after a day of work on a trail crew. Snyder contrasts the Christian myth presented by Milton to the immensity and reality of the natural world surrounding him, and characterizes Milton's vision as a reflection of the "chaos of the mind":

No paradise, no fall,
Only the weathering land
The wheeling sky,
Man, with his Satan
Scouring the chaos of the mind. (Snyder, 1965, p. 8)

The distinction between what is and what is perceived depends on direct experience of nature rather than on interpretations of nature. In fact Satan may *be* that "chaos of the mind" that *is* in some ways definitive of the human. Accompanying the lie of paradise is the lie of the fall, Satan, and "chaos of the mind." Nature is going about its "weathering" and "wheeling," but human beings perceive these events as consequences of natural laws. Nature's continuity and its independence from false human ordering are suggested by the poem's punctuation, the lack of syntactical separation between "the weathering land" and "the wheeling sky." If the book—Milton's *Paradise Lost*—lies, nature does not lie, for it is outside grammar and language, ordering itself beyond human conceptualization. The "clear, attentive mind" described in "Piute Creek" (Snyder, 1965, p. 6), a poem depicting a moment of meditation, foregoes the internalized chaos of meaning in nature and sees both itself and a nature that, being in its own ways sentient, sees mind (and) (as) itself. The contrast between natural process and the "chaos of the mind" in "Milton by Firelight" suggests that the "chaos" Western society finds in nature is an illusion, a "chaos of the mind." Snyder implies that this perception may be based on the belief that divine order must somehow transcend nature. "Truly seen," nature represents not a chaotic face, but a face, seen or unseen, that looks back at us: the face of nature is ultimately the face of the examined self. "Mind" and nature are the same because the "clear mind" sees nature as itself (Snyder, 1965, p. 6).

Practice and *resistance* are therefore intimately connected and potentially interact continuously. Work and meditation as *practices* deliberately *resist* the abstracted face of nature. Contact with mind and matter forces us to establish a sense of relation to earth by making "the world as real as

it is.” Snyder does not see the mind as an evolutionary mistake, as this would be a projection of human valuation onto heavenly creation. Mind can surpass abstraction, and humanity can “break through things as they are” (Snyder, 1968, p. 87), just as it can break things in nature.⁶ “The real work” allows contact with nature through attention to task, but this devotedness becomes problematic when work itself is abstracted rather than attended to directly. Devotion to task is not what a lot of people consider important in work; in a capitalist society, work usually involves maximizing profit. Against the work of “wrecking the world” (“Dillingham, Alaska, the Willow Tree Bar,” Snyder, 1983, p. 92), Snyder advocates the “real work” of saving the world. Snyder thus extends the idea of “the real work” as resistance; humanity’s destruction of nature results from the human ability to self-abstract from nature, to distinguish humanity from what it destroys. Thus, Snyder calls civilization “a lack of faith, a human laziness, a willingness to accept the perceptions and decisions of others in place of your own” (Snyder, 1969, p. 126), and rejects the substitution of culture for nature, the privileging of abstractions over the concrete—a process that creates “self-imposed limitations” to alternative ways of experiencing nature. Against these limitations, Snyder offers “natural” values: “As poet I hold the most archaic values on earth. They go back to the upper Palaeolithic: the fertility of the soil, the magic of animals, the power-vision in solitude...” (Snyder, 1978, p. viii).

The alignment of the heavenly and the human—the natural and the human worlds—bears within itself a route of Dharmic action that that Snyder aligns with the ecological. Put another way, the joining of the heavenly with the human in resistance emphasizes being as an ecological concern. Snyder’s ecological focus reconfigures our relationship with nature. He advances the identity of nature and mind by uniting the “myths” of empowerment that constitute “the most archaic values on earth” with the “texts” of nature. The essay “Four Changes” (Snyder, 1995, p. 32-46), for example, presents the “conditions” of population, pollution, and consumption, and recommends “actions” to solve these problems; yet it also demands a radical “transformation” to generate an ecological life that acknowledges “[w]ildness [as] the state of complete awareness” (p. 41). In this seminal essay Snyder calls for a “reinvention of consciousness” (p. 44) achieved by “seizing the key images, myths, [and] archetypes” (p. 43) and recognizing the possibilities opened by the present:

[W]e are the first human beings in history to have so much of our past culture and previous experience available to our study, and [are] free enough of the weight of traditional cultures to seek out a larger identity; the first members of a civilized society since the Neolithic to wish to look clearly into the eyes of the wild and see our selfhood, our family, there. (p. 45)

This transformation requires development of “psychological techniques for creating an awareness of ‘self’ which includes the social and natural environment” (p. 44). Revolution without “revolution of consciousness” is pointless, while “revolution of consciousness” accepts that “‘man’s survival’ or ‘survival of the biosphere’” are part of “some kind of serene and ecstatic process which is beyond qualities and beyond birth-and-death. ‘No need to survive!’” (p. 45).⁷ Snyder, then, defines “the real work” as the radical transformation of civilization—an end to the globalizing, consumerist, fossil-fuel-based social systems—to an ecologically viable way of life that recognizes the rights of *all* beings. Snyder’s countercultural stance throughout his writings, not to mention in his lifestyle, thus stands as a radical critique of civilization.

He is, of course, aware of the difficulty of this work. “The real work” in fact in many ways becomes the work of a Bodhisattva who “has passed beyond all thought of individuation, or discrimination, or integration [but] retains in mind a memory of the world’s ignorance and suffering, [and] untainted and undisturbed by it, his mind overflowing with compassion ... goes forth in wisdom and love for its emancipation and enlightenment” (Goddard, 1994, p. 655). It involves a continual *practice* that vows *resistance* to the world’s suffering undertaken out of compassion for all beings, human and non-human alike. Further, its accomplishment potentially surpasses lifetimes. The difficulty of the goal is acknowledged as early as the “*Amitabha’s vow*” section of his long poem *Myths and Texts*, where the narrator asks that he “not attain highest perfect enlightenment” if “anyone in my land gets tossed in jail on a vagrancy rap,” “loses a finger coupling boxcars,” or “can’t get a ride hitch-hiking all directions” (Snyder, 1978, p. 45). The “real work” is ultimately emulating Buddha, who “fed himself to tigers”: “a mountain-lion / Once trailed me four miles / At night and no gun / It was awful, I didn’t want to be ate / maybe we’ll change” (Snyder, 1978, p. 14).

3. *Resignation or Acceptance*

Radical effort, because it is so idealistic, is for Snyder a vehicle for spiritual as well as political liberation. “The real work” becomes a movement toward the heavenly, an alignment of human “norms of behavior and ethical rules” with the heavenly “manifestation of reality, of the general state of affairs,” the Dharmic “cosmic law, the ‘great norm.’” In this way work—that which must be done for nature’s salvation—becomes a vehicle for spiritual liberation that involves continuous *practice* and *resistance*.

This brings us to the third aspect of “the real work”—Snyder’s view of *resignation* or *acceptance*. In the poem “The Real Work,” Snyder describes what he sees while boating in the San Francisco Bay around Alcatraz and Angel Island: “sea-lions and birds, / sun through fog / flaps up and lolling, / looks you dead in the eye” (Snyder, 1974, p. 32). Snyder’s linking the sea lions and the sun foreshadows the linkage of human and animal activities at the end of the poem, where Snyder offers us another definition of “the real work”—one that seems as applicable to animals as it is to humans: “the real work. / washing and sighing, / sliding by” (Snyder, 1974, p. 32). The “real work” is simply “sliding by,” doing what we do whether we be gull, seal, or human; and accepting the moment for what it is. “The path is whatever passes” (Snyder, 1974, p. 6); the vehicle of liberation, the ““what is to be done,”“ is acceptance of whatever happens. The non-directiveness of the Zen approach to enlightenment often eliminates intention from action; enlightenment is not achieved through intentionality because intention itself is human projection. Even if a person engages in radical political action, he or she must recognize the need for resignation and acceptance, and “take the struggle on without the *least* hope of doing any good.”

The real work involves taking the world for what it is. As such, it also involves knowing that all human tasks are doomed to failure—failure in the human sphere since people are mortal, and possibly failure in the heavenly sphere, since radical work on earth’s behalf has no guarantee of success. Yet the tasks that shape human life are the only ones that have any significance. To the extent that modern life is based on rapidly disappearing resources, these tasks will survive if

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humanity survives: “all of us will come back again to hoe in the ground, or gather wild potato bulbs with digging sticks, or hand-adze a beam [W]e’re never going to get away from that work, on one level or another” (Snyder & Geneson, 1980, p. 81-82). Gathering food and providing sustenance are all we must do to survive. They are real because “the real work is what we really do” (Snyder & Geneson, 1980, p. 82), and they offer the fullest alignment of human behavior with “the cosmic law, the ‘great norm,’” the “manifestation of reality, of the general state of affairs” that constitutes the *Dharma*. This is the realm of resignation or acceptance that is implied in the real work of Chuang-Tzu’s “heavenly”: “The *real work* is eating each other, I suppose.”

Educational Implications

Although Snyder presents his “real work” in a context that focuses on personal liberation, his ideas hold value for general understandings of developmental and educational processes and practices, and so can shed light on issues related to philosophy of education and educational application. The patterns of practice, resistance, and resignation that make up Snyder’s “real work,” for example, bear remarkable surface resemblance to the basic experience of human development and to features of education in post-industrial society, if not in all societies. From this angle, the (projected) innocence of childhood practice expresses itself in the world of play and repetition, leading to an internalization of patterns, behaviors, pronunciations, formulae, and so on, as has (for example) been famously exemplified in Freud’s description of the *Fort-Da* game, by means of which the child learns about and hopefully comes to accept separation and repatriation, absence and presence. Recall that developmentally, childhood involves the “heavenly” abstraction of the “self” into a separable entity via ego formation, and thus points always back toward the realm of natural expression, a process that the school tries to channel in its effort to inculcate skills, attitudes, and behaviors in the individual. Quite often this initial phase of “self” development evolves into adolescent resistance (rebellion against the status quo, recognized correctly albeit immaturely as an attempt to “tame” the individual, wild, free being of the self; alternatively, the period of ego development leading into the Hegelian/Jungian phase described by Erich Neumann as “unhappy consciousness” in which the emerging, self-conscious ego resists its emergence into consciousness and identity, often through group identification and dangerous behaviors). Frequently the result of unsuccessful resistance—unsuccessful, first, because the self develops anyway, and second, because the world does not seem to change along with the self—is a “resignation” that one can associate with the notorious “deadness” of the student depicted for example by Paolo Freire in his description of the banking concept of education. The chief difference between the above scenario and the Dharmic practice of the real work is the *deliberate insertion of consciousness into the processes* of practice, resistance, and acceptance, and the end result of fuller, heightened awareness, or *acceptance*, rather than a deadening resignation or “dropping out” in the stage of recognition of the world’s force on the individual. Key also is the recognition that resistance is a standard part of this developmental process, and offers the opportunity for channeling or directing such as is described by Paolo Freire (2006).

The Dharmic path thus in many ways reflects—in form—the basic course or experience of modern development and modern education. Recall that Dharma is after all “the general state of affairs” as well as “the saving doctrine or way.” The path of resistance and too often of

surrender results from conflicting messages that encourage retreat or rebellion, efforts to protect the fragile self. This is usually a result of exposure to a world in which conflicting forces tear apart the developing ego even as it tries to find a center to cling to. As Snyder puts it, “Children grow up hearing contradictory teachings: one for getting what’s yours, another for being decent” (“Tawny Grammar,” Snyder, 1990, p. 57). Snyder does not deny the need to teach the *form* of the current social order, nor does he deny that the traditional devices of education should continue. Narration and repetition, for instance, constitute two of the main educational strategies of traditional societies, and they continue their role in contemporary education. Similarly, as Snyder suggests with regard to the language arts, knowledge of contemporary practices is needed for survival both in the system and beyond it:

We can and must teach ... young people to master ... expected standard writing procedures, in preparation for the demands of multinational economies and of information overload. They will need these skills not only to advance in our postindustrial precollapse world, but also to critique and transform it. (“Language Goes Two Ways,” Snyder, 1995, p. 177)

This emphasis on critiquing the world brings *again* to mind Paolo Freire’s (2006) call in *Pedagogy of the Oppressed* for “problem-posing education” as a counterweight to the “banking system of education” that Freire criticizes for its assumption that children are to be the “depositories” of pre-conceived educational values. For Freire, “Problem-posing education is revolutionary futurity” that offers “a means of understanding more clearly what and who [students] are so that they can more wisely build the future” (2006, p. 84). What matters for Snyder, though, is the extent to which the educational practices used will express the “archaic values” that base spiritual being and political action in nature, or whether they will serve the dominant, environmentally destructive paradigm extant in modern society. It is in intentionality that the distinction comes. Education to transform consciousness already exists; education *is* the transformation of consciousness, though consciousness also exists “off the path,” outside of the educative processes per se. In fact, it is frequently in this “wild” realm of consciousness that meaningful learning occurs. The question is not whether consciousness will be transformed by education, but rather *how* it is to be transformed, and *to what* such transformation leads. As Snyder puts it, “If we actually [try] to teach the values of western civilization, [we’ll] just be peddling the ideology of individualism, of human uniqueness, special human dignity, the boundless potential of man, and the glory of success” (“Tawny Grammar,” 1990, p. 62).

Ego formation along the lines of the self-centered and human-centered use paradigms that play into the destructive pattern of “nature as resource” that is leading the world to the brink of environmental collapse is encouraged in contemporary educational strategies via an emphasis on “enlightened self interest” which simultaneously promotes self-centeredness and conformity. This tendency needs to have a counterpart and be penetrated by recognition of the intrinsic value of the (non) self. Adolescent resistance is largely a process of formation via establishment of identity as separate from others, even though so often it is expressed as a type of group identification. The reflection of ego development meets, in the “real work,” its counterweight, where faculties and experience balance against devolution or loss of the self in task or meditation. From this loss of centering in the self comes recognition of the need to transform the self-centered world while simultaneously acknowledging that the world is larger than the ego-

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centered self of experience, though not perhaps the Self (with a capital S) that is so central to Hinduism and other religious perspectives, and that in Buddhism gets expressed as the void. Speaking of teaching in the arts, for instance, Snyder points out that “[t]he occidental approach to the arts—since the rise of the bourgeoisie, if we like—is to downplay the aspect of accomplishment and push everyone to be continually doing something new,” thus emphasizing individual creativity or “uniqueness” rather than, for example, development of a skill:

[In modern society the] emphasis on mastering the tools, on repetitive practice and training, has become very slight. In a society that follows tradition, creativity is understood as something that comes almost by accident, is unpredictable, and is a gift to certain individuals only. It cannot be programmed into the curriculum. It is better in small quantities.... It takes a powerful impulse for a student-apprentice who has been told for eight or ten years to “always do what was done before,” as in the production tradition of folk pottery, to turn it a new way.... (“On the Past, Off the Trail,” Snyder, 1995, p. 147)

Creativity in this model becomes the moment of insight, the wandering “off the path” that affords the true experience of the new. Meanwhile the student in traditional societies had to put up with a teacher who “would test ... patience and fortitude endlessly,” and had no choice but to repeat, repeat, repeat until he “began to experience ... what it was to be ‘one with [his] work’” (Snyder, 1995, p. 146). This is a point of entry into “the real work,” in which the self is lost in the void of the act of creation via repetition. In modern societies, the emphasis on self and creativity as opposed to mastery underlies much education. By removing the accomplishment of the self from the center of education, one may start to move back to a vision of deep-ecological “ethical holism.” As Snyder puts it, “I try to hold both history and the wilderness in mind, that my poems may approach the true measure of things and stand against the unbalance and ignorance of our times” (qtd. in Felstiner, 2009, p. 352).

A further step in this movement away from ego-centered education toward “the common work of the tribe” can be seen in Snyder’s critique of the human-centered perspective that sees nature as a “‘social construction’—a shared cultural projection seen and shaped in the light of social values and priorities” (Snyder, 1999, p. 387). Just as ego-centered education might focus on self and creativity in a way that potentially blocks connection with the other, a human-centered perspective on nature can block recognition of the non-human other as a viable entity with its own self worth. Nature as a “social construction” in this sense too often leads to, while simultaneously feeding, “attacks on nature and wilderness from the ivory towers” that “bolster global developers” (Snyder, 1999, p. 388). This perspective thus connects directly to the now widely acknowledged impending environmental catastrophes of overpopulation, global warming, species loss, and so on. As an initial step in developing a countermeasure to these crises, Snyder calls for developing a fuller awareness of our intimate relation with the environment that should be sustained throughout school systems. For Snyder, this involves education in both the personal place one occupies and in the global environmental problem. He specifies that “Keeping ourselves grounded in our place is very important to us.... [Y]ou can’t work for nature, if you don’t know nature. If it’s just an abstraction then you can’t do it, anymore than you can work on behalf of this or that minority without ever having hung out with them” (Snyder, McCormick & Nancho, 1995). The solution Snyder proposes in this context is a fuller education in the scope of

the natural world, particularly this world as expressed in the immediate natural environment:

it's only one of a number of educational strategies, but it's an educational strategy that should be built into education. It should be built into elementary level education. Just as there should be a much more developed natural history and ecological teaching in elementary school. Just as there should also be, in elementary school up to high school, much better teaching about the monetary system and banking. All of those things are lacking in our basic education.... I'm calling for everybody to learn more, to actually learn more about the planet. And while you're at it learn more about corporate economies.... [B]oth sides are really important.... (Snyder, McCormick & Nancho, 1995)

With regard to educational strategy, then, Snyder calls for further education concerning the natural world—not the natural world as “a realm of resources that has been handed over to humanity for its own use,” but rather the natural world as “a living place for beings who can survive in no other sort of habitat” (Snyder, 1999, p. 387-388). This “living place” is found everywhere, as nature surrounds us in all forms no matter what we do. We are “in nature” as soon as and even before we step outside. Such an education would aim to reduce ego-centered, humanly focussed pragmatics and encourage the recognition of non-human others as entities of equivalent though different validity.

In a time of increasing commodification of education, both as a private corporate structure and in its role as “outcomes centered” resource for the manufacture of workers and consumers, Snyder encourages the development of new perspectives that actually reflect the primal values of emergent humanity that have often been lost in civilization's ongoing drive. Only when education takes fully into account our identity with, dependence upon, and full interaction with nature will it serve to point us back to the path of Dharma, the “general state of affairs” in nature as well as the “duty” or “social obligation” we hold in light of our relation to and existence within nature. These values return us to an ancient, systemic relation with the planet and with ourselves that essentially constitutes the “archaic values” that underlie human nature: “the fertility of the soil, the magic of animals, the power-vision in solitude, the terrifying initiation and rebirth, the love and ecstasy of the dance, the common work of the tribe.” The steps of practice, resistance, and acceptance in Snyder's “real work” outline his own credo and lend veracity to educational strategies that might lead us back to a healing path we long since left.

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Notes

¹ Charles Molesworth, in his book *The Real Work* (1983), uses this phrase to describe Snyder's "establishment of an alternative vision, especially a vision of the role of the poet" which ultimately aims to "[correct] the values of multinational capitalism" by pointing humanity back toward "a total process of nature to which the human species must submit" (p. 3, 9, 6). However, Snyder's articulation of "the real work" also surpasses these political or artistic meanings. The "real work" for Snyder includes a comprehensive practice designed to maximize awareness at all levels—the mundane, the political, and the spiritual. It conveys patterns of intention or attention that link it with spiritual *practice*, with a *resistance* to preconditioned perceptions or understandings, and with ultimate *acceptance* of the First Noble Truth—that existence is suffering.

² "The mercy of the West has been social revolution; the mercy of the East has been individual insight into the basic self/void. They are both contained in the traditional three aspects of the Dharma path: wisdom (*prajna*), meditation (*dhyana*), and morality (*sila*). Wisdom is intuitive knowledge of the mind of love and clarity that lies beneath one's ego-driven anxieties and aggressions. Meditation is going into the mind to see this for yourself—over and over again, until it becomes the mind you live in. Morality is bringing it back out in the way you live, through personal example and responsible action, ultimately toward the true community (*sangha*) of 'all beings'" (Snyder, 1969, p. 92).

³ For an in-depth discussion of practice as spiritual discipline in Snyder's life and work, see Murphy, 1995, p. 97-110. Murphy links practice to process and describes Snyder's evolving practice in relation to Dogen's "Mountains and Waters Sutra."

⁴ Cf. Snyder's description of practice as "Meditation, devotion, dharma-studies, cause-and-effect studies, chopping wood and carrying water, and more meditation yet" (Ingram, Gates, Nisker & Snyder, 1988, p. 25).

⁵ From this perspective, one must recall the Zen Buddhist perception that "[e]arth, water, fire, wind, space *and consciousness* are the elements out of which everything is traditionally said to be composed" (my emphasis) (Hoshin, 1990, p. 67).

⁶ In this light it is interesting to view Snyder's poem "T-2 Tanker Blues" (Snyder, 1965, p. 27-28) as an argument with Robinson Jeffers, a poet who provided an early significant impetus to Snyder's own writing. In fact, Robert M. Torrance (1990) includes Jeffers as one of the "Western" poets that "[e]choes" in Snyder's writings (p. 268). In "T-2 Tanker Blues" Snyder presents the typically Jeffersian perspective of "inhuman" nature and "man, inhuman man" and decides "I will not cry Inhuman & think that makes us small and nature great, we are, enough, and as we are." Along with the philosophical argument, we see Snyder experimenting with Jeffers's prosody, while also parodying it through interjections of personal catastrophe more appropriate to Allen Ginsberg's style than to Jeffers's.

⁷ Snyder elsewhere explains this statement as bearing on the perceptions of the functions of human work discussed earlier. Snyder explains the origin and significance of this phrase:

Nanao Sakaki once said, “No need to survive”—just as we were bundling our leaflets and lacing our boots to do some ecological political exercises [*sic*]. Why this apparent paradox? Quite simple—it’s the same as Dogen’s instructions ‘Cast body away, cast mind away.’ The human world is brought to this pass by an all-too-effective survival consciousness, which breeds anthropocentrism, ethnocentrism, nationalism, parochial localism, and other assorted self-centered uselessly narrow notions of identity. Throwing away these narrow notions of membership helps us to join the mammal world, the vertebrate world, the world of all animals, the world of plants and lichens as well, the world of rocks, sand, clouds, and glaciers, the world of space, the world of emptiness” (Snyder & Woods, 1984, p. 201).